

Supplementary information of *The Cauchy Process on Phylogenies: a Tractable Model for Pulsed Evolution*

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SI-1 Computational Complexity of the Joint Density Calculation

The computation of the joint density described in Proposition 1 of the main document implies two different stages:

- the coefficient computation stage (Equation 0.4), which is recursive and **quadratic** with the number of tips;
- the final density computation stage from the complex coefficients (Equation 0.3), which is **linear** with the number of tips.

Note that the coefficient computation stage does not depend on the the starting value of the evolutionary process. In particular, once these coefficients computed, getting the joint probability density of the tip values with any starting value for the process, i.e. the final stage, can be performed at a linear cost.

SI-2 Ancestral Posterior Distribution

Proof of the Formula We use here the notations from the main text, and prove the ancestral node posterior distribution formula. From the Markov property, conditionally on the fact that the state value Z_n of the ancestral node n is z , the evolution on the subtrees \mathcal{T}_k and \mathcal{T}_l is independent from the rest of the tree. The joint probability density of observing the state value z at n and the vector of tip values can then be written as

$$f_{Z_n}(z, \mathbf{y} \mid \mu, \sigma, \mathcal{T}) = f_{\mathbf{Y}^{\lambda_n}}(\mathbf{y}^{\lambda_n, z} \mid \mu, \sigma, \mathcal{T}^{\lambda_n}) \times f_{\mathbf{Y}^{\lambda_k}}(\mathbf{y}^{\lambda_k} \mid z, \sigma, \mathcal{T}_k) \times f_{\mathbf{Y}^{\lambda_l}}(\mathbf{y}^{\lambda_l} \mid z, \sigma, \mathcal{T}_l).$$

Using Bayes formula, the expression for the conditional density follows.

Computational Complexity To get an idea of the full shape of the posterior ancestral density, e.g., when trying to plot it, one has to compute it for many possible ancestral values z , typically taken from a grid. If we were to use naively the formulas from Proposition 1, getting the posterior density for each point of the grid would be quadratic with the number of tips, yielding a high total computational cost in $O(G|\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{T}}|^2)$, with G the typically high number of values on the grid. However, using the remark of Section SI-1 and the fact that the Cauchy process is symmetric, which allows us to reroot the tree without changing the total probability density, we shall see that this computational complexity can be improved to a much more manageable $O(|\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{T}}|^2 + G|\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{T}}|)$.

Let n be the ancestral node of interest and let \mathcal{T}' be the crown tree obtained by rerooting the original tree to n . Note that

- the tips of \mathcal{T}' are the tips of \mathcal{T} with the same values with the addition of the root of \mathcal{T} with value μ , the starting value of the process;
- n has three direct descendants, says a , b and c , in \mathcal{T}' .

Let us note \mathbf{y}' the vector of tip values of \mathcal{T}' . From the symmetry of the Cauchy process, the joint probability density of observing the state value z at n and the vector of tip values is

$$f_{Z_n}(z, \mathbf{y}' | \mu, \sigma, \mathcal{T}) = f_{\mathbf{Y}', \lambda_a}(\mathbf{y}'^{\lambda_a} | z, \sigma, \mathcal{T}'_a) \times f_{\mathbf{Y}', \lambda_b}(\mathbf{y}'^{\lambda_b} | z, \sigma, \mathcal{T}'_b) \times f_{\mathbf{Y}', \lambda_c}(\mathbf{y}'^{\lambda_c} | z, \sigma, \mathcal{T}'_c)$$

where \mathbf{y}'^{λ_a} , \mathbf{y}'^{λ_b} and \mathbf{y}'^{λ_c} are obtained by reducing the vector \mathbf{y}' to the tip values of the subtrees \mathcal{T}'_a , \mathcal{T}'_b and \mathcal{T}'_c , respectively. Using the remark above, we know that, for each term of the product, we only need to compute the coefficients associated with the density once, with a complexity $O(|L_{\mathcal{T}'_a}|^2 + |L_{\mathcal{T}'_b}|^2 + |L_{\mathcal{T}'_c}|^2)$, smaller than $O(|L_{\mathcal{T}}|^2)$, and then can get its value on any z with an added cost of $O(|L_{\mathcal{T}}|)$, which yields the announced complexity.

SI-3 Increment Posterior Distribution

Proof of the Formulas We first consider the case of a branch ending at an internal node n different from the root. The joint probability density of observing the vector of tip values \mathbf{y} and an increment δ on this branch can be obtained by integrating, over all the possible values z of $Z_{\bar{n}}$ at the direct ancestor of n , the probability of jointly observing \mathbf{y} at the tips, $z + \delta$ at n and z at \bar{n} . From the Markov property, for all ancestral values z , the probability density to be integrated can be written as the product of three factors:

1. the probability density of the increment δ on the branch ending with n , i.e., $f_{\mathcal{C}}(\delta | \sigma t_n)$,
2. the probability density of the tip values of the crown subtree originating at n with $z + \delta$ as starting value,
3. the joint probability density of observing the tips values of the tree obtained by removing all nodes and edges of \mathcal{T}_n from \mathcal{T} and by setting the value of node \bar{n} to z .

We remark that the second factor is equal to the probability density of the tip values minus δ of the crown subtree originating at n with z as starting value. Using the Markov property again, the product of the factors 2 and 3 is the joint probability density of observing the tip value vector $\mathbf{y}^{\lambda_n, \delta}$ of the tree obtained from \mathcal{T} by setting the length of the branch ending with n to zero and the value z at node \bar{n} of this new tree. By integrating this last density over all possible ancestral values z , we get the joint probability density of the tips values $\mathbf{y}^{\lambda_n, \delta}$ of the tree obtained from \mathcal{T} by setting the length of the branch ending with n to zero, which gives us that

$$f_{Z_n - Z_{\bar{n}}}(\delta, \mathbf{y} | \mu, \sigma, \mathcal{T}) = f_{\mathbf{Y}^{\lambda_n}, \lambda_n}(\mathbf{y}^{\lambda_n, \delta} | \mu, \sigma, \mathcal{T}^{\lambda_n}) \times f_{\mathcal{C}}(\delta | \sigma t_n),$$

which is the announced formula. Similar arguments can be applied to all the other cases described in the main text, for the branch ending with the root and all the branches ending with tips.

Computational Complexity Using a trick similar to the one described in the previous section for the node posterior reconstruction, we can reduce the complexity of computing the posterior density of increments ending at the root or ending at a tip on a grid of G values for δ to $O(|L_r|^2 + G|L_r|)$. Unfortunately, the formula for increments of branches ending at internal nodes involves the construction of a new tree \mathcal{T}^{λ_n} , with modified tip values $\mathbf{y}^{\lambda_n, \delta}$, that changes for each value of δ . We hence cannot escape the computation of new coefficients to get the density for each new point, and the computation remains of the order $O(G|L_r|^2)$.

SI-4 Supplementary Figures and Tables

SI-4.1 Simulations: Model Selection

Figure SI-1: Model selection results using the AIC, AICc or BIC for 100 datasets simulated on the Lizard tree (Mahler et al., 2013), with three Gaussian processes (BM, OU, EB), the NIG process with various levels of excess kurtosis (from 1 to 10), and the Cauchy process. All simulation processes but the EB have the same MAD as the BM process with variances σ_{BM}^2 of 5, 10, 50 and 100. For each simulation model, the proportion of time each fitting model is selected is shown as a bar plot.

SI-4.2 Simulations: Parameter Inference

Figure SI-2: Time needed on a standard laptop computer (MacBookPro 13-inch, M2, 2022) for the fit of a CP on pure-birth trees of growing sizes (x axis), using the maximum likelihood with fixed root method (ML, dark red) or the restricted maximum likelihood (REML, light orange). Each boxplot is on 500 replicates.

SI-4.3 Greater Antilles Lizards

Figure SI-3: Profile log likelihood for the dispersion parameters of the svl trait, fitted with a CP using the REML. The likelihood curve is smooth and has a clear maximum, which is a sign that the numerical optimization and likelihood computations went well.

SI-4.4 West Nile Virus

Table SI-1: Fits of Gaussian (BM, OU and EB) and CP models on the WNV dataset from Pybus et al. (2012), on the MMC tree for the latitude and longitude traits. The first two lines are the log likelihood and AIC scores for the ML fit. The parameters are μ for the ancestral root value, σ for the Gaussian standard error or Cauchy dispersion, and θ represents the selection strength α for the OU, and the rate r for the EB. The computation time for each fit on a standard laptop is given in seconds.

	latitude				longitude			
	BM	OU	EB	CP	BM	OU	EB	CP
logLik	-285.68	-285.68	-277.31	-247.97	-352.30	-352.30	-343.93	-308.45
AIC	575.37	577.37	560.62	499.95	708.60	710.60	693.85	620.90
μ	41.20	41.20	41.16	40.81	-75.34	-75.34	-75.54	-74.16
σ	2.80	2.80	7.78	0.40	5.31	5.31	15.67	0.73
θ	-	0.00	-0.53	-	-	0.00	-0.56	-
time (s)	0.00	0.02	0.01	2.04	0.00	0.01	0.02	2.00

Figure SI-4: Ancestral trait reconstruction for the WNV dataset from Pybus et al. (2012), for the latitude and longitudes considered as two independent traits, using the Cauchy REML model fit. Measured traits are shown as a bar plot at the tips of the tree, with a color gradient encoding the trait value, from light yellow (small) to dark purple (large). Modes of the posterior trait reconstructions are showed at internal nodes, with a width proportional to the relative weight of the modes (nodes with only one color have a single mode), and the same color scale as tip values. Modes of the posterior branches increments are showed on the edges, using the same convention, but with a diverging color scale so that increments close to zero are white, positive increments are blue, and negative increments are red.

Figure SI-5: Profile log likelihood for the dispersion parameters of the latitude and longitude traits, both fitted separately with a CP using the REML. In both cases, the likelihood curve is smooth and has a clear maximum, which is a sign that the numerical optimizations and likelihood computations went well.

SI-5 Model Selection with Higher Variance and Gaussian Noise

In this section, we use the same setting as in Section “Model Selection” of the main document, using the fixed empirical tree from the Lizard dataset (Mahler et al., 2013), normalized to unit height, and simulating tip trait datasets using the same evolutionary models, but we either raised the variance of the reference BM process, or added some independent Gaussian measurement error at the tips.

SI-5.1 Higher Variance

In order to check how a higher variance or dispersion affects model selection, we simulated datasets with higher MAD values. We took the variance of the BM as the base parameter, that we varied from $\sigma_{BM}^2 = 1.0$ (as in the main text) to $\sigma_{BM}^2 = 100$. Using the same procedure as in Section “Model Selection” of the main document, we then selected the parameters of the other processes, so that they all had the same MAD values (except for the EB, see main text for more details).

We then applied the same inference and model selection procedure as in the main text for each newly generated tip trait datasets. Figure SI-6 displays the results obtained with reference BM variances σ_{BM}^2 of 5, 10, 50 and 100 (associated MAD are, respectively, 1.51, 2.13, 4.77 and 6.74).

We can see that the graphics are very close one to another and to the results of the main text, with only slight stochastic variations. This suggests that variance or dispersion, i.e., evolution speed, does not influence the model selection accuracy. In particular, a BM with a high variance is not mistaken for a CP with small dispersion, and the jump signature of a CP cannot be captured by a BM (Fig. SI-6).

SI-5.2 Gaussian Noise

In order to check to what extent an additional independent Gaussian noise affects model selection, we simulated datasets with the same parameters as the in Section “Model Selection” of the main document (i.e., with $\sigma_{BM}^2 = 1$), and then added an independent Gaussian error to the tip trait values resulting from each process. We varied the variance σ_{err}^2 of the independent noise from 0.01 to 10.

We then applied the same inference and model selection procedure as in the main text for each newly generated tip trait datasets. Figure SI-7 displays the results obtained with reference Gaussian noise variances σ_{err}^2 of 0.01, 0.1, 1 and 10.

As expected, adding a Gaussian error impairs the accuracy of the model selection, and high amounts of Gaussian noise tend to “cover” the signature of non-Gaussian processes. We however observe that almost 40% of the datasets simulated from a CP with dispersion 0.67 and a Gaussian error with variance 10 are still inferred as coming from a CP. This suggests that the jump signature of the Cauchy process is very strong, and is difficult to erase, even with high levels of Gaussian noises (Fig. SI-7).

As the λ -CP can accommodate for some independent (Cauchy) noise at the tip, we included it in the comparisons on this example (see the *Pagel’s lambda* paragraph of the Discussion of the main text). Here, it improved the results a little, raising the number of cases where the CP (with Cauchy errors) was correctly recovered over a Gaussian process (Fig. SI-8).

Figure SI-6: Model selection results using the AIC for 100 datasets simulated on the Lizard tree (Mahler et al., 2013), with three Gaussian processes (BM, OU, EB), the NIG process with various levels of excess kurtosis (from 1 to 10), and the Cauchy process. All simulation processes but the EB have the same MAD as the BM process with variances σ_{BM}^2 of 5, 10, 50 and 100. For each simulation model, the proportion of time each fitting model is selected is shown as a bar plot.

Figure SI-7: Model selection results using the AIC for 100 datasets simulated on the Lizard tree (Mahler et al., 2013), with three Gaussian processes (BM, OU, EB), the NIG process with various levels of excess kurtosis (from 1 to 10), and the Cauchy process. All simulation processes but the EB have the same MAD as the BM process with variance σ_{BM}^2 of 1. Independent Gaussian errors with variances σ_{err}^2 of 0.01, 0.1, 1 and 10 were added to all the tip values. For each simulation model, the proportion of time each fitting model is selected is shown as a bar plot.

Figure SI-8: Same as Figure SI-7, but including the “λ-CP” in the model selection comparison. When the data is simulated by a CP with Gaussian noise of variance 10 (last column of the bottom right panel) The CP or λ-CP is selected 47 times out of 100, instead of only 40 times if the λ-CP is not considered.

References

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